

Analysis of Start-up Culture, Role of Incubators & Accelerators to Promote New-Generation Enterprises in India

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Abstract

Start-up India, is a flagship initiative of the **Government of India** (launched on January 16, 2016), intends to build a strong eco-system for nurturing innovation & Start-ups in the country that will drive sustainable economic growth and generate large scale employment opportunities. The **Start-up India**, which has got an earmarked corpus fund of Rs.10,000 crores (i.e. Rs.2,500 crore/year, over next 4 years) and is expected to provide a significant boost to the Start-up ecosystem. According to **Global Start-up Ecosystem Ranking Report-2015**, Bangalore is home for about 3,100 to 4,900 active Tech-Start-ups, there by achieving the 2nd highest growth rate for exit volume and Venture Capital investments among the top 20 Start-ups. Currently, **Bangalore is ranked #15** (2015 Rankings) as the only Indian city to be ranked within the **best twenty Start-up ecosystems globally**.

Given this above context, this review paper has presented the analysis of status, influencing factors and growth trends in respect of emergence of Start-ups in India, including Bangalore as Start-up Capital in India, by covering a) Policy framework, b) Growth trends, c) funding options & various schemes for promotion of Start-ups; d) Challenges & Opportunities for Start-ups.

A specific review on the role of Incubators and Accelerators in promoting & nurturing Start-ups is included, including the role of Educational Institutions & Universities. The trend analysis is also being reviewed (NASSCOM, 2015; CII, 2015; Niti Ayog, 2015) & Supportive roles played by Industry bodies like NASSCOM, CII, & other stakeholders; Strategic interventions; Government-Industry-Academia Partnerships and Investors is presented in a comprehensive manner. The Startups landscape & co-working spaces working together in India is also being analysed and presented.

Keywords: Start-up Ecosystem, Start-up Policy in India, Bangalore as Start-up Capital in India, Role of Incubators & Accelerators, Co-working spaces.

Introduction & Rationale for the Study On Start-Ups

Start-ups are the fountainheads of innovation that power this modern world. **Start-up India** is a unique initiative of the **Government of India** (launched on January 16, 2016) which aims to build a strong eco-system for nurturing innovation & start-ups in for driving a sustainable economic growth and generate large scale employment opportunities. This mega- project has corpus fund of

Rs.10,000 crores (i.e. Rs. 2,500 crore/year during 2016-20) for provide a significant nurturing to the Start-up ecosystem. According to **Global Start-up Ecosystem Ranking Reports during 2012 & 2019, Bangalore has been consistently ranked among Top 30 Start-up hubs** (with #15 in 2015 & #18 in 2019 Rankings; Figure 1) and currently, Bangalore is the only Indian city to be ranked within the **best 30 Start-up ecosystems globally**.

Figure 1 Global start-up Ecosystem Rankings-2019 (Source: Compass.co, 2019)

Major Hubs of Start-ups are well-established global cities that have startup ecosystems ranked in the Top-25 with history of high performance. Among the 13 Major Hubs, **nine have been consistently ranked in the overall top 20 since 2012** (Figure2).

Figure 2 Top 30 Global Startup Ecosystems (Source: Compass.co, 2019)

Growth Sub-Sectors: Startup Sub-Sectors (Figure 3) in the **Growth Phase** have increased 4x to 8x in Early-Stage Funding since 2011-2012, compared to 2.5x for all startups

Figure 3 Startup Sub-Sectors in Growth phase (Source: Compass.co, 2019)

Sub-Sector	Early Stage Deals 5-Year Growth	Exits 5-Year Growth, Count	Share of Global Startups	Startup Creation Growth
Advanced Manufacturing & Robotics	107.9%	143.8%	1.8%	6.6%
Blockchain	101.5%	93.9%	2.7%	23.9%
Agtech & New Food	88.8%	74.1%	0.8%	8.3%
AI, Big Data, & Analytics	64.5%	130.3%	7.1%	9.7%

Mature Sub-Sectors: The four startup sub-sectors (**Figure 4**) in the Mature Phase still grew a respectable 15.9% in early-stage funding and 58.6% in exits during the past fiveyears

Figure 4 Startup Sub-Sectors in Mature phase (Source: Compass.co, 2019)

Sub-Sector	Early Stage Deals 5-Year Growth	Exits 5-Year Growth, Count	Share of Global Startups	Startup Creation Growth
Cybersecurity	29.1%	87.3%	0.9%	3.6%
Cleantech	18.3%	26.2%	2.9%	-5.7%
Life Sciences	15.0%	15.0%	2.6%	-7.3%
Fintech	1.1%	105.8%	8.7%	1.5%

Decline Sub-Sectors: Sub-sectors in the Decline Phase (**Figure 5**) are shrinking in terms of early-stage funding deals, although mega rounds and later funding rounds might still be happening.

Figure 5 Startup Sub-Sectors in Mature phase (Source: Compass.co, 2019)

Sub-Sector	Early Stage Deals 5-Year Growth	Exits 5-Year Growth, Count	Share of Global Startups	Startup Creation Growth
Edtech	-15.8%	99.1%	3.1%	0.9%
Digital Media	-38.9%	30.1%	20.7%	-7.5%
Gaming	-40.4%	31.7%	4.5%	-12.0%
Adtech	-47.9%	29.9%	4.2%	-9.8%

Research Gap and Research Problem

The detailed and comprehensive studies on Start-up Ecosystem a rereatively less, when compared to the Silicon Valley in USA, which is major research gap. Hence, this study is a sincere attempt to address it from multiple perspectives.

Another important aspect is that **Public Policy Action Supports Startups & Key Findings on a Global Study (Figure 5, Compass.co, 2019)** indicates:

- a) Efforts to expand funding for startups are the #1 most common policy action taken by governments.
- b) Policy actions to increase access to capital are directly related to greater levels of early-stage-funding inecosystems.
- c) After access to finance, the next-most-common policy action are Startup Support Organizations and Programs (SSOPs) Support & Immigration.
- d) While policy actions have been taken by Govts across various categories, the areas with the least action taken are Bankruptcy, Diversity & Inclusion, and Procurement.

Figure 6 Public Policy Action Supports Startups

Objectives of the Study and Summary

The primary objectives of this study are:

- a) To study the Indian Start-up Ecosystem from multiple & policy perspectives
- b) To assess the factors for successful growth of start-ups in India & related challenges
- c) To evaluate the implications of existing policy frame work on future growth potential of Indian Start-ups & suggest measures for further improvement

Research Methodology

This is an analytical & descriptive study consisting of both secondary and primary research. This analytical research paper has presented the analysis of status, influencing factors and growth trends in respect of emergence of Indian Start-ups, including Bangalore as Start-up Capital in India.

A specific analysis of **role of Incubators and Accelerators** in promoting & nurturing Start-ups is included, including the role of Educational Institutions & Universities. The trend analysis is also being reviewed (**NASSCOM, 2015; CII, 2015; Niti Ayog, 2015**) & **supportive roles played by Industry bodies** like NASSCOM, CII, & other stakeholders; Strategic interventions; **Government-Industry-Academia Partnerships/Investors** is presented in a comprehensive manner.

The primary research work is in progress on study new-generation start-ups especially in the clusters or co-working places like WeWork, 91-Spring Board, etc

Findings of the Study

The findings are presented here below in sub-topics:

Start-up Development Phases & Financing Cycle

The start-ups go through a development phases viz., Ideation, concept formulation, commitment, validation, scaling and final establishment of the enterprise / venture (Figure 6). The start-ups are in various forms at different phases, before going public (IPO) or they may get vanished during any phase of the development cycle (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Start-up Development Phases

Figure 8 Start-up Financing Cycle

According to an estimate by U.S. Department of Agriculture in 2015, the start-ups are contributing significantly to the GDP of global economies, with a projected growth of US\$24.8 trillion for USA, followed by US\$22.2 trillion for China & US\$ 6.6 trillion for India. **Nishith Desai (2015), Bains (2015) & InnoVen Capital (2015)** have documented detailed process of establishing Start-ups, including legal, tax & funding options.

Present Startup Ecosystem in India

India has seen 3 major waves wrt Tech-Startups (Figure 8). The past 10 years have witnessed a tectonic shift in both the overall startup ecosystem in India as well as the ease of doing business. We believe the Union government is doing all the right things, making all the right moves, and showing all the right intents. (Hari and Shradha Sharma, 2018).

Figure 9 Three-waves of Indian Tech-Start-ups

Startup Funding & Investments in India: 2014-18

Altogether \$33.62 BILLION is invested in Start-ups during 2014-18, of which \$13.7 billion was invested in 2017 (Figure 9). Further, in 2017 a record \$13.7 billion was invested across 820 deals, when compared to 2016 (\$4.06 billion) and 2015 (\$8.4 billion) with a higher number of deals with 1,034 (2016) and 913(2015).

Figure 10 Startup Funding in India: 2014-18

Many **crowd-funding and crowd-lending platforms** have emerged as new models for Broader-investment pools to allow individuals to gift, donate or invest in promising creative opportunities, including Rang De, Wishberry, Cash Suvidha, Ketto, Fair Cent, Catapoolt, Fuel A Dream, Bit Giving, Milaap, Impact Guru, Crowder a and i-Lend. E.g., Electric bike Spero was developed by crowd-funding.

Ten Top Companies & Cities for Startup Funding in India –2017

In Indian startup funding ecosystem, the top 10 companies fund-raising account for a bulk of funding (70% in 2017, Figure 10), of which major stake is in Bangalore & NCR region (Figure11).

The rise of **venture debt funds like Trifecta Capital, InnoVen, and Intelle Grow** is now ensuring that start ups do not have to resort only to equity finance to fulfil their capital requirements

Figure 11 Top companies by Funding- 2017

Top Companies by Funding – 2017			
Name of Company	Deals	Value of Funding	Top Investors
Flipkart	4	\$4.12 B	SoftBank, Tencent, Microsoft, eBay
Ola	6	\$1.77 B	SoftBank, Tencent, Tekne Capital, Falcon Edge Capital, Ratan Tata fund
Paytm	1	\$1.4 B	SoftBank
ReNew Power	4	\$740 M	Piramal Capital, JERA
Spandana Sphoorty	3	\$332 M	Kedaara Capital
MakeMyTrip	1	\$330 M	Ctrip.com, Naspers
OYO	2	\$260 M	SoftBank, Lightspeed Venture Partners, Sequoia Capital, Greenoaks Capital, China Lodging Group
Paytm Mall	1	\$200 M	Alibaba Group, SAIF Partners
Janalakshmi	1	\$161 M	TPG (formerly Texas Pacific Group), QRG Enterprises, Treeline
Vini Cosmetics	1	\$156 M	West-Bridge Capital Partners, Sequoia Capital
Total	24	\$9.48 B	

Figure 12 Capital Raised & Deals by City in India

The Walmart-Flipkart Deal by Numbers

A Credit Suisse report estimated that digital payments in **India will grow to USD1 trillion in 2023** from the current \$200 billion.

Finally, **India continues to be the world's fastest growing major economy**, with GDP projected to grow at 7.3 percent in FY 2019, according to the Asian Development Bank. Consumption is expected to only increase. It is hardly surprising why Walmart and others want a toe hold in India.

The detailed case study of Walmart-Flipkart deal will be presented in full-paper, but the highlights

are presented in Figure 12. In December 2017, the Internet user base stood at 481 million. Internet penetration in urban India is at about 65 percent, while that in rural India is a mere 20.6 percent. Considering India’s population of 1.25 billion, there is plenty of room for growth.

Figure 13 Walmart-Flipkart deal by numbers

Women in India’s Startup Ecosystem

In 2018, only **4.5% of the funding deal volume** went to startups with just women founders, while such companies got only around 3% of deal value. However, this does not reveal the full picture, as the largest round by a company with a woman founder was the \$63 million debt round of financial services firm Spandana Sphoorty.

Such startups, including those with **all-woman founding teams, account for around 17 percent of all deal volume** and 9% of all deal value.

A study by **McKinsey Global Institute** in 2015 indicated India can increase its projected GDP in 2025 by between 16% and 60% by getting women to participate equally with men in the economy

A study by **Boston Consulting Group and Mass Challenge**, a network of startup accelerators, found that of the 350 companies examined, the average woman-founded startup received \$935,000 in funding while about \$2.1 million awarded (on average) to the male- founded startups.

A **comprehensive survey of women entrepreneurs** (Your Story and Kstart, 2016) completed to understand the challenges of women entrepreneurs with total of 505 respondents, 90 percent of them women and key findings will be analysed & presented in full-paper

However, the **female-founded startups out performed their male-counterparts’ in bringing in \$730,000 revenue** over 5-year period as against \$662,000 revenue by men: There is hope! Women are equally strong, gutsy, resilient-hardworking as the men. Only thing, they have to find their voices and made sure people hear them.

The Most Active Venture Capital Funds in India

Figure 14 Most active venture capital funds in India India’s ‘Unicorns’

Figure 15 India's 'Unicorns'

 Transportation Founded in Dec 2010 Valuation: \$5.5 billion		
 Foodtech Founded in Aug 2014 Valuation: \$1.2 billion		
 eCommerce marketplace Founded in Jun 2011 Valuation: \$1.1 billion		
 Fintech Founded in 2008 Valuation: \$1 billion		

Waiting to Enter the \$1 Billion Valuation Club

Figure 16 Start-ups Entering \$1 Billion Valuation-club

 Hospitality management Founded in 2011 Valuation: \$850 million		
 Online event ticketing Founded in 2007 Valuation: 500 million		

Figure 17 Chinese Investments in Indian Start-ups by Sectors

Incubators, Accelerators & Investors

In India (2018), almost every IIT and IIMs has an incubator, as do the Indian School of Business (ISB) and the Indian Institute of Science (IISc) and a host of technology and B- Schools. The **Indian STEP and Business Incubator Association (ISBA)** has estimated 100+ incubators and accelerators in India, and centres/institutes like iCreate (International Centre for Entrepreneurship and Technology), **Angel Prime, Startup Village, and Indavest**

Large global companies that have been running accelerator and incubator programmes in India (Figure 16)

Figure 18 Accelerators by Global MNCs

Multinational companies with accelerators in India

QUALCOMM			
BOEING			
SOCIETE GENERALE			
Swiss Re			

Indian companies have also joined bandwagon across sectors with YES Bank, JioGenNext (part of the \$130-billion Reliance Industries Group), and Business World. The industry body of software companies, **NASSCOM**, running the 10,000-Startups incubation programme.

In addition, there are a large number of independent programmes run by privately funded accelerators and incubators such as **Zone Startups, Axilor, T-Labs, Kyron, Social Alpha, Sigma, etc.** The Silicon Valley-based **GSV Accelerator** launched in India(2016).

Incubators for Social Enterprises in India

There is also a growing variety of incubators for Indian social enterprises, over & above NGO-support funds/institutes. E.g., Unltd, a social enterprise incubator launched by Pooja Taparia (2007), has supported >110 social ventures in Maharashtra, by impacting .600,000 beneficiaries. The Dasra Executive Education programme has incubated Milaap, Educate Girls.

Under the Mango Tree, and Mann Deshi. Through the Hubli Sandbox Ecosystem, **Deshpande Foundation** creates an environment to encourage innovative approaches addressing social challenges, thus incubated AquaSafi and Next Drop. **Khosla Labs** supports social ventures in mobile payments/banking, retail efficiency, Big Data analytics and healthcare. IIT-Madras' Rural Technology & Business Incubator (**RTBI**) has incubated Humble Paper, Box Tree, Mobil Train, and Invention Labs. Villgro offers facilities for prototyping and market research and a 12-month in-residence programme; they have mentored >60 startups in the past decade. The Canadian Technology Accelerators (CTA) initiative has been rolled out in India as well, and recently picked 6-Indian startups from Bengaluru, Pune, Hyderabad, andGurgaon.

Startups Landscape & Co-working Spaces Working together in India

Some studies have shown that in the decade following 2006, co-working spaces have roughly doubled every year. According to property consultant **Jones Lang Lasalle (JLL)**, the co-working market in India could touch **16 million seats with an investment value of \$400 million by the end of 2018**. It predicts that by 2025, 42 percent of India's population will be working in urban centres, which will push up the demand for co-working.

Details will be Discussed in full-Paper Regarding

- **91 Springboard** presence in 8 cities with 11,000 seats across 17 facilities
- **Awfis**, >12,000 members in its community.
- Others include InstaOffice, Bombay Connect, Wired Hub, among others.
- Then there's **CoWrks**, large format co-working space provider, backed by real estate group RMZCorp,
- The **Paris-based NUMA accelerator programme** entered India
- global co-working giant **WeWork** entered the market in partnership with the Embassy Group

Co-living also Takes the Roots, with Co-working Spaces & Startups

According to a report in Forbes India magazine, about 600-million people, which is >50% of India's population, below 25 years. This means that there will be an increased demand for living spaces that cater to the needs of a tech-savvy millennial workforce. Key players include StayAbode, ZiffyHomes, CoLife and CoHo. With occupancy at 95-97%, according to BusinessLine investor's interest is high. StayAbode has already received 2-rounds of funding, while CoLife raised \$1 million in funding (2016).

Overnment Schemes for Promoting & Nurturing Startups in India

New Start-up Support : Start-up India, Standup India

The Prime Minister announced the launch of "Start-up India" and "Stand-up India" during his Independence Day Speech on August 15, 2015. The government will promote bank financing for start-ups and offer incentives to enhance entrepreneurship and job creation. Further, the Finance Ministry announced the need to integrate schemes for innovation and entrepreneurship across Ministries, ensure inclusion of remote areas of the country; and promote innovation in terms of new products and processes.

The Budget Speech 2014-15 promised to a) create a technology centre network, b) facilitate forward and backward linkages within multiple value chain and c) setting up of district level incubation and acceleration centers (as per Joint Secretary, Ministry of Skill Development).

Start-up India, is a flagship initiative of the Government of India (launched on January 16, 2016), intends to build a strong eco-system for nurturing innovation and Start-ups in the country that will drive sustainable economic growth and generate large scale employment opportunities. The Start-up India, which has got an earmarked corpus fund of Rs.10,000 crores (i.e. INR 2,500 crore per year, over next 4 years) and is expected to provide a significant boost to the Start-up ecosystem through: a) Simplification and Hand holding, b) Funding Support & Incentives, c) Industry-Academia Partnership and Incubation. With this Action Plan the Government hopes to accelerate spreading of the Start-up movement.

Salient Features of Start-up India Action Plan 2016

- Compliance regimes based on self-Certification:** The main objective is to reduce the regulatory burden on Start-ups.
- Start-up India Hub:** To create a single point of contact for the entire Start-up ecosystem and enable knowledge exchange and access to funding.
- Mobile app and Portal:** Objective is to provide a single platform for the Start-ups to interact with government and other regulatory institutions.
- Legal Support and Fast track Patent Examination at a low cost:** To promote awareness and adoption of IPRs by Start-ups and facilitate them in protecting and commercializing the IPRs by providing access to high quality Intellectual Property services and resources

- e) **Relaxed norms of public procurement for start-ups:** Some relaxation is provided for starts up in government entity and PSU tenders and thus a level playing platform is created to support them.
- f) **Faster Exit of Start-ups:** The action plan has proposed various ways for startups by quickly exiting from a failed situation.
- g) **Provide Funding:** Provides funding support for new development and growth of new Innovation driven enterprises. A corpus fund of rupees 10000 crores has been set aside for this.
- h) **Credit Guarantee funds for Start-ups:** The Start-up plan intends to provide the credit guarantee to all the Start-ups and innovators across all sections of the society.
- i) **Tax Exemption to Start-ups for 3 years:** In order to promote entrepreneurship, government has provided with tax exemption to Start-ups for 3 years.
- j) Launch of Atal Innovation Mission (AIM) with Self-employment and Talent utilization (SETU)

Other schemes of Govt. of India to promote Enterprises & Start-ups

The Finance Ministry has launched the India Aspiration Fund (IAF), which will invest in VC funds with the aim to catalyze investments in Start-ups and MSMEs. SIDBI, LIC India are co-investors. RBI had 31,32 already earmarked Rs. 2000 crores for FY2014-15.

SIDBI Make in India Loan for Small Enterprises (SMILE) is a loan program with a budget of Rs. 10,000 crore launched by the government along with SIDBI. It will offer quasi-equity and term based short term loans to SMEs in the 25 sectors of the Prime Minister's Make in India initiative.

Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency (MUDRA Bank), is a government entity that will provide loans to Start-ups by working with existing banks. It has a budget of Rs. 20,000 crores.)

Key Features of National Policy for Skills Development & Entrepreneurship 2015

Educate and Equip Potential and Early Stage Entrepreneurs

- Developing entrepreneurship curriculum by collecting information and experience from on teaching entrepreneurship from across the world
- Will create an integrated online and offline learning system and deliver entrepreneurship training free of cost through online Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs).
- Will be starting entrepreneurship education in 3000 colleges across India for period of five years, rolled out in phases.
- Entrepreneurship education courses will be provided around 325 industrial clusters across the nation through 50 nodal Entrepreneurship Hubs. Support Entrepreneurship through Entrepreneurship Hubs (E-Hubs)
- 30 state and 50 nodal entrepreneurship hubs to deliver support in addition to the 3000 colleges providing entrepreneurship education.
- This network of E-Hubs will coordinate the delivery of national and state government entrepreneurship support programs and provide access to resources. The E-Hubs will coordinate with industry and other stakeholders as well as lead inter-Ministerial coordination efforts. For example, with programmes such as Atal Innovation Mission (AIM) and Self Employment Talent Utilisation (SETU), or efforts of Niiti Ayog.
- The National Entrepreneurship Hub will be advised by a National Advisory Committee (NAC).

Networks of Accelerators, Incubators and Mentors

- A national network of incubators & accelerators will be set up to support young entrepreneurs. This will be done by 1) supporting existing incubators and 2) support the creation of new incubators.

- A national network of mentors to support entrepreneurs, drawing for example on existing networks and successful local entrepreneurs wherepossible.
- A web and mobile based platform connecting students, young entrepreneurs, mentors, incubators, funding agencies and basic service providers will be established.
- (Source: presentation by Jyotsna Sitling, Joint Secretary, Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, at CII Start-upConclave.)

Atal Innovation Mission (AIM)

AIM is a flag ship initiative of the Indian Government under NITIA ayog to promote innovation, research and entrepreneurship in the country. To ensure that education and research can work in tandem, AIM is setting up incubators in IITs and IIMs. So far, 19 incubators have been selected, while the target is to reach 50+ by the end of 2018.

AIM has also set up Atal Tinkering Labs (ATLs) in schools across the country. These workspaces house do-it-yourself (DIY) kits based on latest technologies like IoT devices, 3D printers, robotics, miniaturised electronics, etc.

With the Atal Innovation Mission, NITI Aayog CEO Amitabh Kant and his team focused on changing an age-old mindset from ‘getting the right job,’ to ‘creating the right job’.

NITI Aayog and its CEO believe “creating an entrepreneurial mindset and bringing a shift towards creating jobs, everyone in India thinks differently and looks at building something that will help the nation at large grow”.

A total of 18 out of India’s 29 states and 7 Union Territories (Figure 17) have announced policies for startups.

Figure 19 Indian States with Start-up Policies (since 2016)

Indian states with startup policies		
Andhra Pradesh	Assam	Bihar
Chhattisgarh	Gujarat	Haryana
Goa	Jharkhand	Karnataka
Kerala	Madhya Pradesh	Odisha
Punjab	Rajasthan	Telangana
Uttarakhand	Uttar Pradesh	West Bengal

Source: Startupindia.gov

Bangalore Ecosystem Phase: Attraction for Ed Tech & FinTech will Be Represented with Data Later in Full-Paper

Reasons for moving startups to Bangalore

- IAC tax exemption: Startups are eligible for tax exemptions for 3-consecutive years out of the first 7years-of-incorporation.
- IT hub: employs about 35% of India’s 2.5 million IT professionals

Implications of the Study

Key Drivers of Indian Startup Ecosystem

- Fast Growing e-commerce Industry in India:** India is the fifth-largest e-commerce market in the world, after China, Japan, Germany, and theUS.
- India on the move wrt Mobile & IoT technologies**
- Learning & Education:** The Internet has deeply impacted the ‘4L’s of Learning’ -- Lecture,

Library, Laboratory and Life, according to Prof. S. Sadagopan of IIIT- Bangalore (in NetChakra: 15 years of Internet in India).

4. **Healthcare** has become one of India's largest sectors - both in terms of revenue and employment, according to IBEF. According to PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), with the segment forecasted to grow to \$ 17 billion by 2021.
5. **Work-Life services:** Digital media is transforming not just the way we learn, work or shop – but also the way we dwell, dine and date!
 - food-tech (Zomato, Wiggly, Fresh Menu)
 - car sales and rentals, transportation, including the ubiquitous Indian three-wheeled vehicle, the autorickshaw (Ola, M-Gaadi)
 - travel and tourism (iTraveller, HolidayIQ)
 - entertainment (BookMyShow)
 - skills and jobs (Vakil Search, My Notice Period, Simplilearn)
 - dating, weddings and parenting (Aisle.co, Baby Chakra, Woo, Shaadisaga).
6. **Payments market:** The Internet and mobile phones are transforming India's banking, finance, insurance, payment and commerce sectors in unprecedented ways, and opening up a range of opportunities for startups in payment, advisory and content services.
7. **Digital media growing in leaps & bounds:** Digital media is transforming India's traditional media giants, creating a digital support system, and spawning a new generation of digital-only pure-play startups
8. **Enterprise products:** Significant transformations are occurring in the organisational world and business ecosystem, which open up opportunities for startups in B2B, B2E and B2B2C products. Notable startups in the space include Freshworks, MuSigma, Capillary Technologies, myNoticePeriod.com, AirWoot, Druva, Dextra and kPoint.
9. **Governance:** The National e-Governance Plan (NeGP) has spelt out e-government and m-government infrastructure, application development and human/institutional capacity building. The Digital India programme aims to take this forward in larger scale (Amit Prakash, Head-Centre for IT and Public Policy, GoI)..

Challenges Faced by Indian Startups

To outsiders, the startup ecosystem appears to be a land of great opportunity but Startups face myriad challenges from all quarters – government regulations, fund raising, lack of mentoring, scaling correctly, managing cashflow and even finding the right employees

1. Lack of funding
2. Cash burn to revenue
3. Finding the right people
4. Lack of regulations
5. Lack of clear strategy
6. Lack of mentorship
7. Fighting perceptions

Conclusions & the Road Ahead

India jumped 30 points to reach the 100th spot in the World Bank's ease of doing business global rankings (2017). It was reason to celebrate, especially since anumber of Indian startups have chosen to register abroad because of restrictions with respect to foreign ownership and investment in different sectors.

With one of the largest populations and consumer bases in the world, **India has enough potential to be both producer and consumer, which means that Indian startups have a wide range of consumer classes, products and services, and business models to choose from.**

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